

**IMUFLAM – A POTENTIAL THERAPEUTIC APPROACH IN THE TREATMENT OF POST-
COVID-19.
SHARED OWN EXPERIENCE**

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Abstract

Signs and symptoms of illness that persist for more than 12 weeks and are not explained by an alternative diagnosis are most commonly described as persistent Covid-19.

The development and severity of Long Covid does not seem to correlate with the nature of the symptoms in the acute phase of the infection. Large health systems in the US and England often offer various therapeutic options to deal with prolonged Covid, including physical therapy, mental health support, but still lack sufficient pharmaceutical options.

There is already sufficient scientific data on natural products with immunoregulatory and anti-inflammatory effects. IMUFLAM- belongs to the group of compounds with therapeutic potential against the new respiratory corona virus.

Referring to the data from scientific publications and already accumulated clinical experience, we applied Imuflam as part of the therapeutic solutions of patients with Covid-19, after their discharge, with the aim of influencing the long-term health consequences of our patients. The clinical observation covers 30 patients hospitalized during the period from 01.11 to 30.11.2021. in the Gastroenterology Clinic of St. Marina UMBAL, Varna.

Patients were drawn into 3 groups of x 10 patients

Ist group – applied treatment with Imuflam in a dose regimen of 2x1 caps

II-nd group took nutritional supplements without a doctor's prescription (vitamin D, vitamin C, selenium, zinc, vitamin B12).

III-th control group. The assessment was carried out on the 15th and 30th day of the application of Imuflam, respectively food supplements without a doctor's prescription. In the first 15 days, no significant differences in clinical complaints were observed in the three groups of patients, which did not apply to the period of 30 days after admission.

Keywords: *Post-Covid-19, Immuflam, nutritional supplements without a doctor's prescription, cognitive dysfunction, quality of life.*

Full abstract

For millions of people around the world, the health impact of contracting the coronavirus extends far beyond the initial period of infection. This, for the United Kingdom, amounts to more than 2 million adults, or about 3.5% of the country's population. As more evidence of long-term Covid infection emerges, Professor Paul Elliott, program director of the REACT Imperial School of Public Health, paints a grim picture of the long-term health consequences of Covid-19, based on their findings. Signs and symptoms of illness that persist for more than 12 weeks and are not explained by an alternative diagnosis are most commonly described as persistent Covid-19.

Common symptoms of Long Covid include: extreme fatigue, shortness of breath, chest pain and tightness, persistent cough, concentration and memory problems. Other symptoms include: sleep disturbance, palpitations, dizziness, pain in joints and muscles, this is only part of the complaints of more than 2/3 of those who have recovered from the Covid infection. An analysis of 1,077 patients in the post-hospital Covid-19 study (Phosp-Covid) in the UK found 'clinically significant' symptoms of anxiety and depression in ¼ of participants significant' symptoms of anxiety and depression in ¼ of patients.

Fig. 1 The long-term effects of COVID-19

Source: Reproduced with permission from SIMPLECOVID (2020)

A large proportion of patients cannot return to their previous social life "Many describe how it affects mental health, especially as the course of the disease often varies, the moment they feel they are getting better 'symptoms come back.' Scientists from the University of Manchester found a link between long Covid and the change in the immune system of patients six months after hospitalization. However, the development and severity of Long Covid does not seem to correlate with the nature of symptoms in the acute phase of infection. Large health systems in the US and England often offer various therapeutic options to deal with prolonged Covid, including physical therapy, mental health support, but still lack sufficient pharmaceutical options.

New drugs in development focus on reducing inflammation and restoring mitochondrial function. People with prolonged Covid report turning to a wide range of over-the-counter medications, nutritional supplements, other therapies and dietary changes to manage relapsing and remitting symptoms. Many patients are willing to try anything because the symptoms have a significant impact on the quality of life of those affected.

A number of studies have shown that there are potential risks of self-prescribing a number of medicines, leading to many harmful drug interactions and the use of inappropriate treatments. A large percentage of people look for online resources, including medical blogs and journals. Due to the small evidence base, these platforms are potential source of conflicting information and misinformation. Current and future harmful effects of polypharmacy need to be assessed. There is no doubt that there is an urgent need for research and health support to improve the recovery period after a past Covid infection. Based on the

scientific data on unrelenting immune dysregulation, it is more than clear that it is necessary to think long-term about its control, as well as about dealing with the infection.

A new study published on 04/01/2021 by Alabama-USA demonstrates that immune dysregulation does not subside even after the infection has been controlled, but continues for more than 2 months. There is already sufficient scientific data on natural products with immunoregulatory and anti-inflammatory effects. IMUFLAM- belongs to the group of compounds with therapeutic potential against the new respiratory corona virus.

Imuflam - also available for use in Bulgaria - a two-component combination of highly standardized extracts proven to treat COVID-19. Contains 350 mg of Cat's Claw (*Uncaria tomentosa*) extract and 150 mg of *Tanacetum parthenium* extract.

Cat's Claw - the cat's claw acts mainly as an immunomodulator and provides protection to the body against viruses, bacteria and fungi, balances the cytokine $TNF\alpha$, thereby controlling inflammation. The anti- $TNF\alpha$ action of Cat's Claw defines it as a natural biological agent. There are also data on other effects of *Uncaria tomentosa* extract, namely antimutagenic, antioxidant, antiaggregant and tonic effects. *U. tomentosa* demonstrated a significant in vitro inhibitory effect on the replication of herpes simplex virus type.

The administration of *Uncaria tomentosa* during vaccination shows increased effectiveness of the pneumococcal vaccine, due to an increase in the lymphocyte/neutrophil ratio in the peripheral blood. Evidence for the antiviral properties of Cat's Claw points to the extract as a possibility for use in COVID-19 as well.

Tanacetum parthenium - The extract of Tanacetum parthenium contains substances from different chemical groups, -sesquiterpene lactones, flavonoids, etc. The biological substance against which the standardization of the extract was carried out is parthenolide. 150 mg of extract contains a high amount of parthenolide - 0.6 mg, which determines its high

efficiency. The remaining ingredients, flavonoids, including the well-known antioxidant quercetin, increase the effectiveness of the extract through the synergistic action with parthenolide. It has anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, anti-migraine, anti-tumor and antioxidant effects.

Figure 2- Immunoregulatory and anti-inflammatory activity

Hyperinflammatory changes in COVID-19 result from immune dysregulation, leading to excessive production of proinflammatory cytokines. Treating immune dysregulation and inflammation early in the course of COVID-19 prevents disease progression and improves prognosis. Immune dysregulation does not subside for a minimum of 2 months after a relapse of COVID-19. Imuflam has a high antiviral, immunoregulatory and anti-inflammatory effectiveness, while at the same time it has an excellent safety profile with long-term use.

Referring to the data from scientific publications and already accumulated clinical experience, we applied Imuflam as part of the therapeutic solutions for Covid-19, after their discharge, with the aim of

influencing the long-term health consequences of our patients.

The data are from patients hospitalized in the Gastroenterology clinic of the UMBAL "St. Marina" in the period from 01.11 to 30.11.2021. In the first 15 days, no significant differences in clinical complaints were observed in the three groups of patients, which did not apply to the period of 30 days after admission.

Group 1 patients showed better clinical response to symptoms and restored quality of life. Patients from group 2 have a positive dynamic of complaints, but a slower impact of complaints compared to group 1. In the control group, the slowest impact of symptoms was observed for the observed period of time.

Tab. 1

Period of recovery of patients to normal daily life

	20-30 yrs.	30-40 yrs.	40-50 yrs.	50+ yrs.
IMUFLAM	Up to 2 weeks	Up to 2 weeks	Up to 2 weeks	Up to 1 month
DIFFERENT ADDS	Up to month	Up to month	Up to 1 month	Above month
CONTROL GROUP	Above month	Above month	Above month	Above 2 months

Tab. 2

Degree of disruption of daily life of control group patients

	20-30 yrs.	30-40 yrs.	40-50 yrs.	50+ yrs.
Up to 2 weeks after sickness	high	high	high	Really high
Up to 1 months after sickness	medium	medium	high	Really high
Above 1 month after sickness	medium	medium	high	high

Tab. 3

Degree of disruption of daily life in patients taking sporadic nutritional supplements

	20-30 yrs.	30-40 yrs.	40-50 yrs.	50+ yrs.
Up to 2 weeks after sickness	high	high	high	Really high
Up to 1 months after sickness	medium	medium	high	Really high
Above 1 month after sickness	medium	medium	high	high

Degree of disruption of daily life of patients taking Imuflam

	20-30 yrs.	30-40 yrs.	40-50 yrs.	50+ yrs.
Up to 2 weeks after sickness	medium	high	high	high
Up to 1 months after sickness	low	medium	medium	high
Above 1 month after sickness	low	low	low	medium

The clinical observation covers 30 patients, men and women aged from 24 to 73 years - average age. Patients were drawn into 3 groups of x 10 patients

1st grade - applied treatment with Imuflam in a dose regimen of 2x1 caps

2nd c. took nutritional supplements without a doctor's prescription (vitamin D, vitamin C, selenium, zinc, vitamin B12). III - control groups.

The diagnosis was confirmed with a PCR test. The most common symptoms during the hospital stay are grouped into the following: shortness of breath, cough, fatigue, headache, muscle pain, chest pain, abdominal pain, diarrhea, depressive experiences.

Clinical and laboratory indicators showed a too wide range of deviation from normal values.

Markers of inflammation, ferritin, DKK, continued to be observed even after discharge, but already against the background of treatment with Imuflam 2x1 capsule.

It was impressive that even a mild course of Covid infection is associated with medium-term symptoms requiring follow-up and treatment.

Patients were followed up on the 15th and 30th day of discharge, as the inclusion of Imuflam, we estimated that it would manifest its therapeutic effect without the risk of other drug interactions.

Among the selected evaluation parameters, we included: memory disorders, fatigue, depressive tendencies, difficulty breathing, headache, muscle pain.

Patients were asked to rate their complaints on a scale of 1-4.

The assessment was carried out on the 15th, 30th and 60th day of the application of Imuflam, respectively, dietary supplements without a doctor's prescription.

In the first 15 days, no significant differences in clinical complaints were observed in the three groups of patients, which did not apply to the period of 30 days after admission. Group 1 patients showed better clinical response to symptoms and restored quality of life. Patients from group 2 have a positive dynamic of complaints, but a slower impact of complaints compared to group 1. In the control group, the slowest impact of symptoms was observed for the observed period of time. The most frequent persistent symptoms are - shortness of breath - 9%, fatigue - 5%, numbness of upper and lower limbs - 5%, memory disorders - 8%. Cognitive dysfunction or memory impairment was found to be common in all age groups.

The group of patients up to 40 years of age were more likely to have headaches, abdominal pain and anxiety/depression, and the age group over 50 years. share significantly more shortness of breath, chest pain, fatigue, and cognitive impairment. In addition to markers of inflammation, reactive changes in liver

enzymes led us to conclude that non-alcoholic metabolic fatty liver disease may be an independent risk factor for a more severe course of infection, but together with this in control studies on day 15 after discharge values up to 1.5 above the upper limit of the norm were found at baseline - three digits.

The application of Imuflam shows an extremely good tolerability profile, influencing the main laboratory indicators and quality of life. We found that patients from all three groups included in our observation report a significant impact on their functional status after relapse. Age, severity of the disease and the presence of existing co-morbidities are some of the important risk factors for the development of the syndrome after COVID-19.

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